

H.H. Munro's *The Lumber Room*: A Lacanian Reading

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Abstract: The association of psychoanalysis and literature is a common thing which comes for a long period. This paper attempts to discuss the engagement of Lacanian concepts of psychoanalysis with H.H. Munro's (Saki) one of the notable short stories "*The Lumber Room*". The story depicts the powerful imaginative power of the main character named Nicholas and his authoritative aunt. The main character: Nicholas' aunt draws him into a psychological collapse and he escapes from that affliction, with the support of his imaginative power. As the methodology it is followed the method of textual analysis, giving attention to the protagonist's traumatic experience of *The Lumber Room* and his imaginative power under Lacanian psychoanalytic criticism. Therefore, the keen attention is given only for Lacan's concepts, not for the ideas which generated by the father of psychoanalysis: Sigmund Freud. Further the study provides a clear alignment on the character Nicholas, his traumatic experience which undergoes due to his aunt and how he escapes using his affluent imagination collaborating psychoanalytic criticism of Jacques Lacan. Finally, the story is observed through the Lacanian perspective in order to fulfill the objective of the study.

Keywords: Psychoanalysis; Jacques Lacan; *The Lumber Room*; H.H. Munro; imaginative power

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Introduction

Literature is not simply a mirror to life but it expresses the ulterior motives, hidden, and unknown factors which have never been found or which are uncanny to be expressed through any other medium. *The Lumber Room* is a notable short story written by Hector Hugh Munro (Saki), focusing on a persona called Nicholas and about his aunt. This has been claimed by many to have autobiographical bearings, but one should be astute at the same time because when a text that too a literary text when seen as a documentary or autobiographical or history or anything else other than a narration, kills the text in the process of reading and the interpretation of such a process will become like an operation on a cadaver. With ill-treatments by the aunt, Nicholas undergoes traumatic experiences but is able to escape the trauma

due to he being affluent in his imagination. In order to decipher the modus operandi of the power of imagination amidst the traumatic downfall, the theories of Jacques Lacan become an expert tool.

Widyalankara in a paper entitled *The Lumber Room: Ideal Artifact for Prose Analysis + An Epistle on Chile Rearing* states that self-esteem, mental health, and academic performance of a child can be affected when it reads the short story *The Lumber Room* since it works as a symbol transforming the inner self of a child when it is a potential reader. Even though Widyalankara tries to do a Prose analysis by pulling out lines from the short story and trying to paraphrase them, her analysis heavily misses the intertextual elements and the theological aspects in order to clearly decipher the workings of the texts.

In his book *Reading Saki The Fiction of H.H. Munro* by Brian Grisbon, commented as follows, Ethel Munro has declared, connecting Nicholas and Saki while threading the aunt with their cousin aunt Augusta who collected frustrations, nostalgic and tinged memoir for Saki's 1870s childhood. "...guardians watchful eye" is a remembrance of Saki's aunt while maintaining psychological retreat which caused to move Nicholas inward similar to Saki. Then he adds, Nicholas uses his own imaginative power to describe the tapestry as a child but there is a deficiency because he talks about the psychological retreat and imaginative power with different extremes. (Gribson)

Fonseka mentioned in *Punishment as Misdirected Discipline: A Psychological Study of 'The Lumber Room' by H.H. Munro alias Saki*, readers can observe how the aunt's punishments psychologically effect on the protagonist. Then he states inside the Lumber room Nicholas was able to release from his depression that always burn him, without giving a considerable space to Nicholas' endeavor that he exerts to escape from that burden. Further, *Ironical Symbols in Saki's Stories* Kaya observes Saki's, "*The Open Window*" which symbolizes Mrs. Sappleton's heartbreak and sorrow draws her through the loss of her family encounters; her husband and younger brother using the open window itself. Therefore, it shows that as a wounded child with loss of proper love and affection, Munro has fed his unconscious feelings not only into *The Lumber Room*, but also for his other short stories.

It is perceivable that available literary works show the gap how Nicholas' aunt draws him into a psychological collapse as well as how he escapes from that affliction, threading his imaginative power. Further, due to this study attempts to emerge with the Lacanian psychoanalytical perspective, previous theory which formed by Sigmund Freud and other scholars' engagements regarding the linguistic signs have not been brought up here into the consideration.

Objective

To read traumatic experience of the main character of *The Lumber Room* and his escape from the trauma with his affluent imaginative power under Lacanian psychoanalytic criticism.

Theoretical Considerations

Psychological criticism or psychoanalysis refers writers or their characters under the psychological lens and explores the state of mind. Sigmund Freud is the father of this criticism who deeply explained the mind, and behaviour. Then later Jacques Lacan (French Freud), the French psychoanalyst radically extended and revised Freudian concept and explained it under a different perspective. According to Lacan "*Language is no used to reveal our unconscious rather language is our unconscious which governed by the rules of the signifier as it is language*". Further, he stated that readers can only know someone's unconscious through particular speech and language that they use. And as the central concept of Lacan's psychoanalytic theory is, "*the unconscious is structured like a language.*" (Homer, 2005)

Lacan interpreted that there are three different orders or registers which involve to guide our psychological life naming, The Imaginary, The Symbolic and The Real. They are intertwined as Borromean rings similar to if one is broken, the entire structure can be separated. Explaining it further, The Imaginary is the period (6 – 18 months) of the development of the Ideal I (Ego). Within this period (also known as the Mirror stage), a child starts to identify it as a different creature on a mirror. This is the "small other" due to our imagery starts and ends with our existence. Then with the next stage;

The Symbolic order, an individual starts to define their identity using a language rather than a mere image. Because language is not as same as the image i.e. it never starts and ends with our existence, and it becomes the “big Other”. The Real which comes with neo natal stage escapes the articulation of the language or The Symbolic order. With Lacanian perspective, each and every human who lacks or loss something with their personality passes these three stages. And they use a particular language to express their pains.

Moreover, considering the concept of the Linguistic sign, even other critics mainly Ferdinand de Saussure interpreted the ‘sign’ under the following diagram,

Sign → $\frac{\text{Signifier (word or sound image)}}{\text{Signified (concept or mental image)}}$ Lacan reformulated it uttering that a sign should be interpreted as a capital

Signifier which is over the signified while trotting out the bar as a barrier to the particular meaning. Lacan insists the signified is something that always remain hidden with signifiers. (Savarimuttu, 2016)

Signifier
signified

Research Methodology

As the methodology it is followed the method of textual analysis, giving attention to the protagonist’s traumatic experience of *The Lumber Room* and his imaginative power under Lacanian psychoanalytic criticism. The story can be analyzed under three divisions respectively, as the psychological collapse of Nicholas, his plans that he practiced and launched to enter into the Lumber room and the Lumber room and his imaginative power.

Discussion

Here the researcher attempts to show how far the short story is observed through the eye of Lacan’s theory which significantly talks about the language and unconsciousness. For that psychological downfall of Nicholas and the way he uses his imaginative power are considered here. According to psychoanalytic, literary texts are used to express the secret unconscious desires and anxiety of authors through characters that they use. H.H Munro can be considered as a writer who faced a lot of problems during his childhood with the loss of his mother. With many evidences the aunt of the particular story is similar to his aunt Augusta with whom Saki spent his childhood. Therefore, the story provides evidences to express his secret childhood pains through the protagonist of “*The Lumber Room*”.

The psychological collapse of Nicholas

The psychological collapse of Nicholas can be initialized to interpret with the very first paragraph of the short story. [THE CHILDREN WERE to be driven, as a special treat... Nicholas was not to be of the party; he was in disgrace... – Saki] As a matter of fact whatever the behaviour that people put into the outer world is the result governed by unconscious mind. With the Lacan’s speech “*The Insistance of Letter (1957)*” he talks about “The concept of Lack”, which is explained, every person lacks or loss something in his/her personality. As the entire story victimizes Nicholas, the protagonist lacks with love, affection and kindness by his aunt with her military nature which caused him to be in disgrace. Family is one of the major factors that impacts on the final product of everyman (Tyson). Throughout the story there is no any clue regarding his mother or father. Only about his authoritative and unheedful aunt, and few cousins.

The story reveals the way she treats children as a self-righteous and moralistic person. Further, ironically the writer demonstrates the way children were being brought up with aunt as following. [Older and wiser and better people had told him that there could not possibly be a frog... – Saki] She thinks about herself as a wiser person while not listening to children. She tries to keep children away from beautiful places and things and she is having a sack of rules and regulations which uses to govern small children. To clarify this idea further we can come across with some words such as, “expedition”, “offender”, “gardening operations”, “watchful eye”, “sentry-duty” and “rigorously debarred” which are particularly

used with military services. Therefore, aunt's treatments and the nature of the aunt leads him to behave disgracefully and that is why at the beginning we, readers read Nicholas as a naughty boy with wild and violent nature.

His pain removes the aunt away into an emotional distance providing evidence that is Nicholas' ignorance to help the aunt for coming out from the rain water tank. Moreover, this weak relationship can be assumed while finding the aunt's name. Readers can observe that Saki has not given a proper name to the aunt instead of he addresses her as "soi-disant", "a woman of few ideas", and "the Evil one". It highly symbolizes the bond between these two characters. Finally with the above illustrations readers can cycle both actions of aunt's and the reaction of Nicholas' as the result of an emotional wound that automatically brings him into a psychological collapse. Therefore, the distant relationship that happens due to the protagonist's psychological collapse with his aunt can be connected with Lacan's theory while giving a considerable place to his concept of language and unconscious mind engaging into Nicholas' imaginative power that he uses to run off from his pain.

Launching strategies

With the first plan which is revealed in the story, putting a frog into the breakfast, Nicholas literally captured his necessity because he wanted to drive his cousins away in order to enter into his plan even though the aunt took him away from the treat of Jagborough. And it is the first step of his intention, to execute his long-germinated plan. When moving forward, it is clear that Nicholas is with a clear plan. He used to practice opening locks to overcome his intension since he does not have enough experiences to fit the key into keyholes as a child. Comparing these actions with the process of psychoanalysis it can be clarified as, Nicholas wanted to step out his first stage even getting insulted. And then this boy who does not believe too much luck sailed his long-term plan even amid his aunt's hypocritical behaviour. Saki has converted these all into verbal form repeating several crucial situations which Nicholas has to encounter. Aunt's wickedness and insults are not an accidental occurring. The writer shows it as her nature which causes to make a distance between Nicholas and the aunt as aforementioned. Moreover, that *important-looking key* can be compared to his curiosity and anxiety and putting a frog into the breakfast can be consciously taken out while verbalizing his plans. Hence, all these actions which Nicholas admitted to enter into the Lumber room are similar to the process that caused to take out the powerful unconscious. In another words he uses the plans to flow his imaginative power freely out.

The Lumber room and powerful imagination

The entire story happens due to Nicholas needs to enter into the Lumber room that exists beyond his presence. That is the way to escape from his mental disturbances. His desire to enter there resembles on his curiosity and anxiety to cope up with his creativity and imaginative power. Saki introduces the Lumber room as a "*large, dimly lit place*" as well as a "*store house of unimagined treasures*". It is similar to the unconscious mind where people buried the strongest and the deepest thoughts, feelings, failures, and pains which equals to the dark and valuable Lumber room.

The writer tries to bring out the aunt's character symbolizing the adulthood as a psychological barrier to the world of imagination, creativity, joy and fantasy. Therefore, the woman of few ideas plays the role as the signifier who breaks the child's world while pulling Nicholas into the symbolic order which contains lack or loss. Here the writer clearly projects the imaginative power out with Nicholas' explanations about the possibilities of the scene of the tapestry. That was the reason, *To Nicholas it was a living, breathing story*. Nicholas passes *golden minutes* with his powerful inner thoughts due to he is fully free. With the explanations regarding the Lumber room similar to the unconscious mind of Nicholas, here, Lacan's ideas can be taken out as "*Language uses do not reveal our unconscious rather language is our unconscious*". Further, the 'signified' remain hidden here similar to his equation since the writer point his finger to the entire adulthood.

Summation

The study discusses about *The Lumber Room* by Saki under the Lacanian psychological perspective using the textual analysis. It is explored the protagonist's unconscious mind connecting his power of imagination i.e. the study dives into the way how Nicholas, the protagonist comes out from a psychological downfall which appeared due to his aunt,

through his imaginative power. Further, this study encourages researchers to use parallel literary criticisms as Freudian concept, to adjudicate the story.

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